

The Preparation of the Substituted Butyrolactams.

BY SARBBANI SAHAY GUHA SIRCAR.

The following work was undertaken with a view to supplement the work already published in connection with the influence of groups and associated rings on the stability of certain heterocyclic ring systems (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1227, **131**, 600, 1252, 1257; *ibid.*, 1928, **133**, 898.) The systems previously studied under the above heading were, respectively, the substituted glutarimides, succinimides, paracanic acids and the butyro- and valero-lactones. Though the actual study of the relative velocity of the ring fission in the present series of compounds has not been found immediately possible owing to the unsatisfactory nature of the reactions so far studied with this end in view, the preparation and the properties of the compounds themselves are of sufficient interest to justify the present communication.

The preparation of a series of alkyl substituted γ - or δ -amino-acids or their lactams cannot be accomplished by the various methods already known for the preparation of such compounds (*cf.* Fischer, *Ber.*, 1904, **37**, 3063; 1906, **39**, 351; Gabriel, *Ber.*, 1891, **24**, 2452; 1908, **41**, 513, 1127, 2010; Mendius, *Ber.*, 1895, **28**, 1949; Engel, *Ber.*, 1875, **8**, 1597; Tafel, *Ber.*, 1886, **19**, 2414; 1894, **27**, 2313; Haller and Bauer, *Compt. rend.*, 1914, **158**, 1086; Blaise, *C.*, 1899, [ii], 524; Wallach, *Annalen*, 1900, **312**, 171; Schotten, *Ber.*, 1883, **16**, 644) mainly on the ground of difficulty in obtaining the suitable intermediate compounds, specially in the case of the *gem*-dialkylated derivatives.

A simple way out of the difficulty would seem to be the reduction of the imides of the dibasic acids (glutaric and succinic) which might be expected to yield the lactams by the simple reduction of one of the carbonyl groups in these compounds, but a number of attempts at such reduction involving the use of zinc or tin and hydrochloric acid, iron and acetic acid, hydriodic acid (with or without phosphorous), or sodium and alcohol, failed to give the desired products. The difficulty seems to lie in the slow velocity of the reduction process as compared with the ease with which the imides hydrolyse into the corresponding acids and ammonia. Negative results were also obtained when the lactones corresponding to the lactams (Sircar, *loc. cit.*) were heated with urea or ammonia, or

when the silver salts of the imides were heated with ammonium iodide.

The various methods above described having failed to give the desired product, Hofmann's reaction, applied to the imides of the glutaric acids was ultimately resorted to. This method has been employed with success by Hoogewerf and van Dorp (*Rec. trav. Chim.*, 1891, 10, 4) in the case of phthalimide and succinimide, and has been improved upon by Lengfeld and Stieglitz (*Amer. Chem. J.*, 1906, 15, 215, 518) who obtained a number of derivatives of β -aminopropionic acid, by its means. Noyes (*Ber.*, 1894, 27, 917) introduced a slight variation in the procedure in the case of camphorimide by opening the imide ring with hot alkali before adding bromine. As, however, there is a large range of variation in the stabilities of the various substituted glutarimides (Sircar, *loc. cit.*) required for this purpose, the employment of hot alkali involves the risk of incomplete ring-fission in some cases, and the further hydrolysis of the first formed amic acid (into the glutaric acid and ammonia) in the others. To overcome this difficulty, it was found advisable to decompose the anhydrides of the various substituted glutaric acids (which are less stable than the imides in all cases) with ammonia, in order to form the amic acids. This reaction is fairly rapid and does not involve the risk of further change. The ammonium salts of the amic acids thus obtained were then converted into the corresponding sodium salts and the latter treated with hypobromite as in Hofmann's reaction. The details of the method will be found in the experimental portion. The following scheme give the series of reactions involved.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The substituted butyrolactams were prepared by a slight modification of Noyes' method applied to camphorimide. The suitable glutaric anhydride was treated with 2.2 equivalents of concentrated ammonia solution (sp. gr. 0.89), when a vigorous reaction ensued.

When this subsided, the mixture was heated on the steambath for $1\frac{1}{2}$ hours to complete the reaction. The excess of ammonia was also removed in part by this treatment. After cooling, the ammonium salt of the amic acid was decomposed by a slight excess of equivalent amount of sodium hydroxide solution (10 per cent.) and the liberated ammonia removed under reduced pressure at 40-50°. This process was generally complete when the solution was concentrated to half its volume. The solution of sodium glutaramate thus produced was next added with stirring to a cold solution of potassium hypobromite made by dissolving one equivalent of bromine in 8 equivalents of 10 per cent. caustic potash solution (900 c.c. of 10 per cent. potash and 10 c. c. of bromine for $\frac{1}{2}$ molecule of the anhydride). There is a small amount of effervescence at this stage due to a certain amount of free ammonia remaining in the solution. The mixture was then gradually heated in a water-bath to 70-75° and kept there for two hours.

When the reaction was over, the solution was somewhat concentrated by distilling off some water from a sand-bath. This procedure also decomposed any unchanged amic acid. The solution was then cooled and neutralised with concentrated hydrochloric acid after adding some sodium bisulphite to decompose the unchanged hypobromite. In the case of the diethyl and the *cyclohexane* derivatives some of the lactam was at this stage thrown out and was extracted with ether. The solution itself was then strongly acidified with concentrated hydrochloric acid, and evaporated to dryness on the water-bath. The residue was introduced into an extractor and exhausted first with ether and then with alcohol or acetone, the former solvent removing some of the glutaric acid (formed from the amic acid). The acetone extract was evaporated to a pasty consistency to remove the excess of hydrochloric acid, dissolved in a small amount of water and carefully neutralised with 10 per cent. caustic soda solution in the cold. The mixture was then extracted with pure ether several times, the latter dried with potassium carbonate and distilled.

The lactams thus obtained can be distilled without decomposition under ordinary pressure, though the boiling points are fairly high, higher indeed than the corresponding butyro- and valerolactones. They are thick colourless liquids or low melting solids with a characteristic smell when liquid. They are moderately soluble in water and very soluble in all the usual organic solvents

including light petroleum. In all these solvents they tend to form supersaturated solutions and come out as fairly big flattened rhombic prisms. They are neutral in reaction and moderately stable towards dilute acids and alkalis. They are precipitated from aqueous solution by phosphotungstic acid (white precipitate), mercuric acetate (white), lead acetate (white), tannic acid (white), Meyer's reagent (yellow), or Dragendorff's reagent (deep brown). With 3:5-dinitrobenzoyl chloride in alkaline solution they give a deep violet colouration.

The butyrolactams form crystalline additive compounds with mercuric chloride in aqueous solution. These compounds, however, slowly decompose into their components on warming their solutions in water or organic solvents. Yellow oily gold chloride addition compounds are formed in ethereal solution, which could not be obtained in the crystalline condition. Yellow, oily or crystalline nitroso derivatives (nitrosamines) are obtained when the lactams are dissolved in dilute sulphuric acid solution and a solution of potassium nitrite is added in the cold. In the case of the higher members this derivative soon solidifies and can be crystallised from ether-petrol. The lower members are however liquids. All of them give the Liebermann reaction. The nitroso derivatives are gradually decomposed in warm aqueous solution, and much more rapidly in the presence of alkali. Unstable silver derivatives of the lactams are obtained by adding an alcoholic solution of silver nitrate to the sodio-derivatives formed by the addition of an equivalent of sodium ethoxide in alcohol to the lactams. On warming, these derivatives decompose, leaving a silver mirror.

The lactams also form crystalline benzoyl derivatives under Schotten-Baumann conditions. The lower members, however, form liquid derivatives.

cycloHexanespirobutyrolactam was obtained from *cyclohexane* diacetic anhydride in 46 per cent. yield, m.p. 98°, b.p. 180-181°/13 mm. It crystallises in flattened tetrahedra from petrol (b.p. 40-60°). (Found: C, 70.45; H, 9.9; N, 9.0. $C_9H_{13}ON$ requires C, 70.6; H, 9.8; N, 9.1 per cent.). The *benzoyl* derivative crystallises from petrol in stout needles, m.p. 138°. (Found: C, 74.5; H, 7.3; $C_{16}H_{19}O_2N$ requires C, 74.7; H, 7.4 per cent.). The *nitroso* derivative crystallises from petrol in needles, m.p. 82°. (Found: N, 15.2. $C_9H_{14}O_2N_2$ requires N, 15.4 per cent.). The mercuric chloride *addition product* melts at 158-160°.

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cycloPentanespirobutyrolactam was obtained in 38 per cent. yield, m.p. 75°, b.p. 164°/16 mm. It crystallises from petrol in large flattened tetrahedra, and has a great tendency to form super-saturated solution in this solvent. (Found: C, 69·05; H, 9·2; N, 9·8. $C_8H_{13}ON$ requires C, 69·06; H, 9·35; N, 10·1 per cent.). The benzoyl derivative crystallises from petrol in needles, m.p. 70-71°. (Found: C, 73·8; H, 7·0. $C_{13}H_{17}O_2N$ requires C, 74·1; H, 7·0 per cent.). The nitroso derivative crystallises from petrol-ether in long needles, m.p. 51-52°. The mercuric chloride addition compound melts at 135°.

$\beta\beta$ -Dimethylbutyrolactam was obtained in 35 per cent. yield, m.p. 65-66°, b.p. 146-147°/12 mm. It crystallises from petrol in diamond-shaped crystals. (Found: C, 63·55; H, 9·7. $C_6H_{11}ON$ requires C, 63·7; H, 9·7 per cent.). The benzoyl derivative crystallises from petrol, m.p. 69°. The nitroso derivative melts at 45°. The lactam has also been described by Blaise (C., 1899, [i], 874).

$\beta\beta$ -Methylethylbutyrolactam was obtained in 30 per cent. yield, m.p. 74-75°, b.p. 150-152°/13 mm. (Found: C, 66·0; H, 10·2; $C_7H_{13}ON$ requires C, 66·14; H, 10·23 per cent.). The nitroso derivative is an oil which could not be solidified.

$\beta\beta$ -Diethylbutyrolactam was obtained in 40 per cent. yield, m.p. 76-77°, b.p. 163°/12 mm. (Found: C, 67·9; H, 10·5. $C_8H_{15}ON$ requires C, 68·1; H, 10·6 per cent.). The mercuric chloride addition product melts at 130°.

β -Ethylbutyrolactam was obtained in 25 per cent. yield, b.p. 117-118°/13 mm. (Found: C, 63·5; H, 9·5. $C_6H_{11}ON$ requires C, 63·7; H, 9·7 per cent.). The nitroso- and the benzoyl derivatives are liquids which failed to solidify.

β -Methylbutyrolactam was obtained in 15 per cent. yield, b.p. 116°/15 mm. (Found: C, 60·4; H, 8·8. C_5H_9ON requires C, 60·6; H, 9·1 per cent.).

Butyrolactam was obtained in 20 per cent. yield, b.p. 114°/14 mm. (Found: C, 56·4; H, 8·1. C_4H_7NO requires C, 56·5; H, 8·2 per cent.).

In attempting to apply the method of ring-fission employed in the other series of compounds (imides, paraconic acids and lactones, *loc. cit.*), it was unfortunately found that the lactam ring is very much more stable than the other rings so far studied. Thus equivalent alkali in N/200 or N/100 solution produced very little effect in three hours in the case of the first two members and even heating

in the presence of N/10 alkali for 5 hours at 55° produced fission to the extent of less than 10 per cent. A similar observation has been recorded in the case of oxindole by Baeyer (*Ber.*, 1883, 16, 1704) who found that this lactam has to be heated with a solution of baryta to 150° in order to bring about complete fission. As the employment of such drastic conditions would necessarily take away the value of the quantitative data so obtained (by introducing disturbing factors), and especially as it would involve greatly increased difficulty of experimental manipulation, it was ultimately decided, after a number of unsuccessful attempts, to abandon the method rather than collect data of doubtful value by its means. The preparation of the lactams, however, is not without interest as very few members of this class of compounds are known and as their properties have not been studied in detail by any previous worker.

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THE IMPERIAL COLLEGE OF SCIENCE AND
TECHNOLOGY, LONDON.

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